

**The Role of the International Law in Shaping the Governance for Sustainable
Development Goals**

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Abstract

Human needs are grown with the emergence of Post – 2015 Agenda forwarding the new global ‘sustainable development goals.’ To address the challenges in achieving global goals, the mechanisms, ideas and notions presented so far are valuable and significant and somehow provide a course of action. However, a clear mechanism establishing the linkages between the elements and principles of policymaking and effective implementation is still missing. The scope of global goals is universal arising from the long standing of international law instruments and their delivery is domestic. However, the fragmented nature of the instruments of the international law is a challenge, but a review of previous mistakes in governance mechanisms shows that the gaps can be filled by establishing the principled application of the elements of governance with the principles of international law.

Keywords: Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs); International Law; Governance; Principles; Policymaking.

1 Introduction

Plato said, ‘whenever we try to achieve, we plan,’ terming the ‘human needs’ as achievements accomplished through the ‘plan’ as strategies. The ‘plan’ and ‘achievements’ are the core phenomena of governance arising from the Greek word ‘kubernáo,’ which means ‘to steer’(Rampersad & Hussain, 2014). The authoritarian governments in medieval times used to plan and strategise in pursuit of the essential needs of the public (Nicholson, 2016). Evolved civilisations transformed the strategies into governance due to the growth in the needs of increasing populations across the globe (Greenberg, 2007). Hence, the governance to achieve human needs is not new, and it is continuously evolving to meet the growing needs of humans. The human needs, which were food, shelter and health are now processed as quality food, decent living-conditions, good-health and well-being.¹

Globally agreed with the needs of the present and upcoming humans since the adoption of the Post – 2015 Agenda are 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs or goals) (Tosun & Leininger, 2017). SDGs are distended form of sustainable development, and they are to certify the economic, social, and environmental needs of the humans (Fukuda-Parr, 2016). They aim at sustainable use of natural resources and the protection of the environment, as well as social and economic development. These aims are arising from the international law instruments, including, treaties, declarations and conventions, because SDGs are a realisation of human rights, environmental protection, and sustainable exploitation of natural resources (Kim & Bosselmann, 2015).

¹ Due to emergence of Sustainable Development the human needs were progressed, (Brundtland, 1987); The human needs are constantly changing, see: (“Introduction to Social Welfare, Introduction to Social Welfare Policy,” 1980)

SDGs appeals effective implementation employing hierarchical, subsidiary, empowered and real-time multilevel governance.² As output social, economic and environmental policymaking processes, the SDGs have attained much attention from institutions, academics and policymakers.³ The growing concerns in the practical implementation of the SDGs have accelerated diverse ideas.

Despite the new orientation of the emerging ideas, there is a lack of collaboration and cooperation among implementing institutions (Pogge & Sengupta, 2015). It is observed that the forwarded governance mechanisms are fragmented and are not convincing enough to establish a conclusive framework by ascertaining all the SDGs (Stevens & Kanie, 2016). Similar approaches are being approved in governance as were adopted for the unsuccessful implementation of ‘sustainable development’ (Polk, 2011). The sustainable development was also stemmed with the assistance of international law, propositioning the ‘good governance’ as its crucial part (Kardos, 2012). The failure to achieve ‘sustainable development’ is due to discoordination, disagreement and conflict among the implementing institutions (Runde & Savoy, 2014).⁴ The problem with the mechanism of good governance lacking a principled approach to build institutional coordination and symmetric hierarchies, which are a viable part of effective implementation.

SDGs as an advanced form of sustainable development adopted through the doctrines of international law calls for principled governance. Furthermore, the literature highlighting

² Multilevel governance is a mechanism of implementation involving cross-sectoral, hierarchal, subsidiary, top-down and bottom-up institutions. (Hub, n.d.-b)

³ The term ‘institutions’ in this research is adopted in generic sense because this research is not focusing on specific issues related to States, Regions or local government, the focus is on theoretical development of governance applicable on all the modes of governments. See for example, (Beisheim & Simon, 2018)

⁴ There are plenty of lapses in implementation mechanism with good governance principles and elements, (Runde & Savoy, 2014).

the causes of previous failures suggests enhancing the elements of governance by providing them with a shape to achieve targets effectively. Hence, the governance mechanism for the SDGs necessitates revisiting the principles of international law and the literature on effective governance (Peters, 1998; Rhodes, 1997). However, before initiating a new governance mechanism for implementation of SDGs, it is essential to observe the impediments in existing approaches.

Therefore, this research aims to analyse the flaws in existing approaches and proceeds theoretical solutions with the *modus operandi* of principles of international law shaping the SDGs. SDGs are the expectations of the global community to meet their needs, and there is an opportunity to develop a conclusive and inclusive governance framework devising policy and implementation mechanism (Le Blanc, 2015).

2 Impediments in Existing Approaches

Good governance is integrally connected with the sustainable development envisioning the best practices of policymaking and building efficiency of institutions (Nanda, 2006). It directs the institutions in a particular manner for effective implementation and addresses the issues raised (Kardos, 2012). The theoretical values of good governance eradicate instability, corruption, abuse of the law, poverty and inequality (Smith, 2007). Hereafter, it was expected that the practice of good governance would be improved with time for future development.

The contemporary developmental realm is revolutionised comprising the democratic governmental structures (Weiss, 2000). In this realm, throughout the last decade, good governance has become controversial due to its broad generalisation (Ferreira, 2008). Such oversimplification in good governance has caused institutional inconsistency in

devolved and decentralised governance structures. Good governance in evolutionary governance models is weak to ascertain interactions among policy and institutional mechanism of implementation (Botchway, 2000).⁵ Theoretically, there is a lack of harmonisation between the elements of policymaking and institutional mechanisms (Wong & Guggenheim, 2005; World Bank, 2017c). Practically, there are asymmetries in decision-making power within the hierarchies of implementing institutions (Morin & Orsini, 2013; World Bank, 2017c).

The redressal of the issues of inadequate coordination by thriving the elements of good governance establishes useful means of implementation. The elements of good governance have mushroomed in different types of governance mechanisms, namely, multilevel, effective, equitable and meta-governance building interplays of various practices (Kooiman & Jentoft, 2009).

For instance, Meadowcroft et al (2005) expedite in ‘multilevel governance’ the element of ‘participation’ as ‘enhanced participation of social institutions’ in order to balance and protect the enlarged interests of the society. Similarly, Kemp et al (2005) while defying current strategies as un-sustainable in development, explicates the elements of ‘equitability,’ as ‘common objectives,’ and ‘sustainability-based criteria for planning.’ The elements of ‘coherence’ and ‘efficiency’ as the rules enhancing institutional capacity and promoting coordination are illustrated in the form of ‘policy integration,’ ‘shared mechanisms,’ ‘incentivising implementation,’ and ‘encourage innovation.’

⁵ In general, there are element of good governance, however, the linkages among these elements are quite weak and the reason behind theory and implementation, see, John O Kakonge, ‘EIA and Good Governance: Issues and Lessons from Africa’ (1998) 18 Environmental impact assessment review 289; and, Katharina Hoffmann, ‘The EU in Central Asia: Successful Good Governance Promotion?’ (2010) 31 Third World Quarterly 87.

Meadowcroft et al (2005) opined that the elements evolve in multilevel governance, drawing cross-connections among institutions. According to Kemp et al (2005) sustainability is in pursuit of integration of governance, because it is all at the same time about protection (of the environment), creation (of just world, society and economy) and is in pursuit of (economic, environmental and social) stability. Diversity is inevitable, and surprise is unforeseeable, hence, 'precautionary measures' and 'preventive action' are to be taken when there is a threat to sustainability.

On the other hand, Meuleman and Niestroy (2015) uttered that the thriving principle to reform institutional mechanisms would be the 'common but differentiated governance.' The goals are common, and diversity is common too, to achieve them, institutions have to set targets and timelines (Meuleman, 2018). The timelines indicating the sub-targets are to be created involving the institutions holistically (Meuleman & Niestroy, 2015). The institutional integration shall be vertical as well as horizontal creating 'reflexivity' due to interfaces of science and policy, and, law and economy.

While envisioning a 'meta-governance framework' for implementation of SDGs, Meuleman and Niestroy (2015) attributed the elements of the 'rule of law,' 'transparency,' 'inclusiveness,' 'responsiveness' and 'participation' to develop more 'accountable institutions.' The means of implementation are in the form of goals as 'policy integration,' 'institutional networks,' 'capacity building,' 'partnerships,' and 'selective participation' through the elements of 'coherence,' 'efficiency' and 'participation.' Accordingly, meta-governance is coordinated means of implementation, which includes hierarchal, market and network, and its key characteristics are to link the elements with goals for implementation.

Conversely, the United Nations University scholars, Biermann et al (2014) encouraged the old elements with futuristic methods. The elements of ‘consensus,’ ‘participation,’ ‘coherence,’ ‘cohesion,’ ‘transparency’ and ‘accountability’ are linked with the policymaking (good governance). ‘Efficiency,’ ‘responsiveness,’ ‘certainty’ and ‘predictability’ are related to implementation (effective governance), and ‘equitability’ and ‘rule of law’ are aimed at equitable distribution of wealth and opportunity (equitable governance). According to Biermann et al (2017), the implementation of SDGs heavily relies on the strong linkages among the ‘multilevel governance’ from policymaking to implementation and finally, distribution of outcomes.

Biermann et al (2017) lodges that multiple indicators are available to determine effective policies and implementation. The futuristic techniques and application of the elements are delved in the governance of interaction among sustainability, environment and society. Perhaps the SDGs open space for well-tailored indicators useful for governance principles. Therefore, the tool of international law is to be followed, to manage networks of institutions and adopt scientific evidence while driving policymaking, as suggested by Zeijl-Rozema et al (2008).

Zeijl-Rozema et al (2008) further elaborated that the mechanism of ‘monitoring’ and ‘evaluation’ (transparency and accountability) is to regulate the institutional implementation. The critical requirements of governance for sustainable development are ‘long-term focus (science and policy interface),’ ‘integration of ecological, economic and social processes,’ and ‘structuring engagement’ following the institutional interaction while carrying implementation.

A report prepared by the United Nations Economic and Social Committee, Committee of Experts on Public Administration and Department of Economic and Social Affairs

(UNESCO Report) is with a pragmatic perspective promoting 11 principles in real-time 'multilevel governance' for implementation of SDGs (Hub, n.d.-a). Firstly, the three principles of 'competence,' 'sound policymaking,' and 'collaboration' affixed with effectiveness in governance (Bouckaert et al., 2018). Secondly, the principles of 'integrity,' 'transparency' and 'independent oversight' are integrated for the accountability of institutions. Thirdly, the principles of 'leaving no one behind,' 'non-discrimination,' 'participation,' 'subsidiary' and 'intergenerational equity' are attached with inclusiveness.

UNESCO Report considers that sound policymaking is to originate 'coherence' in diverse goals enabling institutions at all levels to 'collaborate' in implementation. The principles of 'transparency' and 'independent oversight' are to arrange the links between disclosure of information and review of decisions to hold institutions liable. The principles of 'leaving-no-one-behind', 'non-discrimination,' 'participation,' 'subsidiarity' and 'intergenerational equity' are to allow the public-at-large, institutions and non-governmental groups to involve in policymaking as well as implementation (Bouckaert et al., 2018).

A study conducted by the Policy Department of the European Union on 'Europe's approach to implementing the SDGs: good practices and the way forward (EU Study)' fosters the same principles as adopted by the UNESCO Report, but with different motion (Niestroy et al., 2019). EU Study establishes the principles of 'interconnectedness,' 'indivisibility,' 'universality' and 'integration' for coherent policymaking to flourish partnerships, coordination and shared responsibility across governing institutions. The principle of 'accountability' as 'monitoring' and 'reporting' is demonstrated for open review processes and to maintain the integrity of the institutions. The principles of

‘inclusiveness’ and ‘universality’ are to ensure ‘intergenerational and intragenerational justice’ and dispense long-term perspectives.

However, the complexity is regarding diverse pattern of interlinked policies due to enlarged interests of the various stakeholders (Chin, 2016). Carrying out the effective implementation of interconnected but overlapping policies is challenging for the institutions. The effective implementation is not limited to institutions of central or provincial/State governments, there are local institutions to interact, and there is an immense amount of private sector (Aziz, 2012).

In contemporary policy mixes, the elements of governance reflect through an interplay to create an impact in implementation. The element of the ‘rule of law’ for impartial implementation of law in contemporary mixes of policy is determined by a coordinated institutional capacity to enforce the decisions effectively (Hanson, 2014). The heterogeneity in policies urges the institutions to work with the long-term orientation while protecting the interests of each group (Nee & Opper, 2009). Additionally, the interests of individuals are protected by holding institutions liable for their decisions under a transparent mechanism of access to information (Rigobon & Rodrik, 2005). Therefore, the elements of accountability and transparency also relate to the rule of law differently.

The element of participation allowing the individual, groups and organisations to influence the decision-making process in contemporary governance is quite challenging (Conroy & Berke, 2004). The decision-making process for one policy impacts the other because the issues are intertwined. To build consensus is hard and assimilation of diverse interests is complicated (Lindsay, 1993). The diverse interests of institutions are turned

as the main contention causing other grave threats of corruption, dishonesty and dis-integrity (Indumati & Ramapriya, 2015).

The conflict among the institutions defies the position of law and policy generating uncertainties in authority to implement decisions (World Bank, 2017a). The power asymmetries can undermine policy effectiveness and the unequal distribution of power in the policy arena can lead to exclusion, capture, and clientelism. The issue of imbalance powers in hierarchies is often ignored while devolving the authority and subsidiarity in decentralised governance mechanisms. Disproportional division of powers make way to inequitable means of implementation and are the principal cause behind ‘(un)sustainable development.’

Sustained policies are certain and predictable with the focus of long-term outcomes (Roy & Tisdell, 1998). Focusing on long-term results in consistent policies is in conjunction with precautionary measures and preventive action (Theys, 2002). Effective policies build competent and efficient institutions developing and maintaining the adaptive capacity to respond to the interlinked matters and provide cross-learning opportunities spatially (Janssen & van der Voort, 2016). The responsive capacity of institutions is judged in a timescale and demands the policy frameworks to be designed in a manner bringing-out competitive advantage (Holweg, 2005).

The functional aspect of institutional responsiveness emanates from the capacity-building, competitiveness, efficiency and adaptiveness (Janssen & van der Voort, 2016). Effective implementation optimally pursues continuity and update of competent policies, maintained and sustained via appropriate administrative and political frameworks, and are for co-existence of the institutions (Joshi et al., 2015). The legitimacy is the core concern for appropriateness of political frameworks and is resolved through the

impartiality providing equal treatment and eradicating corruption (Kronsell & Bäckstrand, 2010).

Other elements curbing corruption are transparency and accountability and are corroborated using robust reporting, independent auditing and competitive procurement systems (Hale, 2008). Transparency means reporting and monitoring, and accountability is a review of the institutional acts and decisions. Such a review of the actions and decisions were previously limited to the external institutional mechanisms (Marceau & Hurley, 2012). However, now to maintain ‘integrity,’ as a concrete notion of the accountability, the reviewing powers are safeguarded in the form of the mechanisms of code of conduct for officials, whistle-blower protection, effective systems of scrutiny and access to justice (Latimer & Brown, 2008; Teweldebirhan, 2013).

Although the successful reforms are basically to design interlinked policies by ameliorating elements of governance. However, prior to the adoption of the reform agenda, the necessity is to visualise transformative models of governance. Since the contemporary model of governance is a new public management of socio-cybernetic systems and self-organising networks (Roe, 2013). These self-organising and socio-cybernetic management systems coincide the institutional hierarchies for decision-making and implementation (Guimon, 2014). This approach is multilevel/meta governance, and it establishes the links between policymaking and effective implementation through diverse elements and practices (Meuleman, 2008).

At this juncture, the elements of good governance cannot be ignored because of their constant role in policymaking and implementation. The elements of good governance shall be revisited with the prospective approach to unfold the policies for institutional commitment, cooperation, coordination and trust. The elements and principles of

governance are flexible in means of practices; at the same time, they have perpetual roles and outputs (van Buuren et al., 2014).

Good governance helped to achieve quite many targets of sustainable development (Brinkerhoff, 2007). The poverty and hunger have been significantly reduced, stable institutions are ensuring equitable implementation of the law, and global leadership is considerably working to mitigate environmental degradation. Nevertheless, the risk has not curtailed; the SDGs arises in the form of warning against the misconceptions that something is worth (Lu, 2016). The climate emergency, health hazards, collapsing forests and dilapidating biodiversity are among other next immense challenges.

World Bank, (2017c, 2017d) expects the change from international actors and urges to adopt such preferences which reshape the incentives and think about ‘role of law.’ The ‘role of law’ in governance is primarily eternal, enabling institutions to cooperate in the implementation of diverse targets with a principled approach. International law is the primary source of change in the jurisdiction of international actors and has forwarded global agenda.⁶ Therefore, the principles of international law are revisited to design a governance framework for the implementation of the SDGs.

⁶ International law plays a significant role in governance to ensure sustainable outcomes, see for example, Nicholas G Onuf and Richard K Birney, ‘Peremptory Norms of International Law: Their Source, Function and Future’ (1974) 4 *Denv. Journal of International Law and Policy* 187; and, Christine M Chinkin, ‘The Challenge of Soft Law: Development and Change in International Law’ (1989) 38 *International & Comparative Law Quarterly* 850.

3 Connecting Elements of Governance with the Principles of International Law

The progressive literature redressing the impediments of governance for sustainable development and SDGs retreats valuable suggestions.⁷ Howbeit, the difference of opinion increases complexity while propositioning the principles/elements of/for the governance of SDGs. Contrarily, the most prominent feature of all these principles and elements is that they arise from the basic principles of international law.

The role of international law is complicated but concrete when it is dedicated in a manner of converging the elements of governance with the approach of reshaping preferences through principles (von Bogdandy et al., 2010). The problematic elements even thrived, but without principles and law inflict the institutional discoordination and fragmentation in policies (Jachtenfuchs & Krisch, 2016). Contrariwise, the principles are with the focus of targets because they are not laws, they are benevolent, and their practice shapes them to a malevolent version in the form of elements, components and tools to produce results (Young, 2017).⁸ Therefore, the principles construing SDGs are to be linked with the elements of governance to orchestrate the means of effective implementation.

‘Intergenerational equity’ is the fundamental principle inherited from the notion of sustainable development (Barral, 2012). Hence, besides ‘intergenerational equity’ SDGs are for ‘intragenerational equity,’ and both of these equities are of evolutionary value in

⁷ This research does not intend to explore and analysis exhaustive literature, the available best literature has been extracted and cited to draw prospective conclusions. The references and notes suggest that the research has analysed a variety of literature on governance, SDGs and sustainable development.

⁸ The principles of international law effective in governance are with the approach of implementation, see, (Meuleman, 2018) and (Bouwen & Taillieu, 2004).

international law, driving the sustainable development to SDGs (Kaufmann & Grosz, 2008).

‘Intergenerational equity’ is to ensure equitable and proportional exploitation of natural resources in order to protect the environment and preserve resources for future generations (Arrow et al., 1995). ‘Intragenerational equity’ is to distribute wealth and opportunity ‘equitably’ and ‘proportionally’ among existing generations (Braveman & Gruskin, 2003). The paradigm of ‘equity’ in SDGs postures the principle of ‘proportionality’ which means that the action must be rational and reasonable in achieving a permissible goal (Franck, 2010).

Biermann et al (2014) specify ‘equity’ and ‘proportionality’ in the form of ‘equitable governance’ as a mechanism to distribute wealth and opportunity.⁹ The EU Study and the UNESCO Report affirms ‘equity’ and ‘proportionality’ as ‘intergenerational justice,’ to preserve the natural resources for future generations (Bouckaert et al., 2018; Niestroy et al., 2019). Meadowcroft et al (2005) recognised that ‘proportionality’ is an action appropriate to the scale of a problem, which means that the implementation should be rational in achieving a goal. Zeijl-Rozema et al (2008) identify that ‘equitable’ economic growth is the future towards ecological and cultural preservation. Meaning thereby, ‘equity’ through ‘equitability’ is the genes of the sustainable development and goals (Barral, 2012).

Meuleman and Niestroy (2015) suggested that maintaining ‘equity’ and application of ‘proportionality’ espouses to take a long-term approach. Kemp et al (2005) convey comparable advice that long-term methodologies in the exploitation of the natural

⁹ Equitable Governance for equitable distribution covers the principles of ‘proportionality and equity,’ see, (Biermann et al., 2014)

resources are affirmed by adopting ‘precautionary measures’ and ‘preventive measures’ to attain a level of certainty and predictability. Thus, maintaining ‘equity’ and applying ‘proportionality’ in sustainable development coerces to take ‘precautionary measures’ and ‘preventive action.’¹⁰

In accordance with the international law approach of governance, the ‘precautionary measures’ and ‘preventive actions’ are to take pre-emptive measures prior to any act which may be proportional to the livelihood of others (Trouwborst, 2009). ‘Precautionary measures’ and ‘preventive actions’ are fundamental principles of international law which mean to take pre-emptive measures before exploitation of natural resources (Tedsen & Homann, 2013).

The UNESCO report and the EU Study promotes long-term planning and ecosystem management by taking impact assessment measures (Bouckaert et al., 2018; Niestroy et al., 2019). Impact assessment is carried out with the ‘precautionary measures’ and ‘preventive action’ (Tickner & Geiser, 2004). The policymaking for SDGs is based upon precaution in the form of impact assessment through evidence, knowledge and learning.¹¹ Zeijl-Rozema et al (2008) attributed the long-term planning with ‘precautionary measures’ to maintain the sustainability of society and the physical environment.

The exercise of ‘precautionary measures’ is to attain a level of proportional and equitable exploitation of natural resources because the complexity lies in ‘interrelatedness’ and

¹⁰ Precautionary measures and preventive actions are basic principles of Convention on Biological Diversity and are taken for long-term approaches, see, Andy Stirling, ‘Precaution, Foresight and Sustainability. Reflection and Reflexivity in the Governance of Science and Technology’ [2006] *Reflexive governance for sustainable development* 225; and, Eckard Reh binder, ‘Precaution and Sustainability: Two Sides of the Same Coin?’ [1994] *A Law for the Environment: Essays in Honour of Wolfgang E. Burhenne* 93.

¹¹ The governance for sustainable development is evidence based, therefore, the governance for SDGs is to be more evidenced based as it is distended form of development goals. See, (Hertin et al., 2009)

‘interdependence’ of the biophysical, ecological, and environmental (Lozano, 2008). ‘Interrelatedness’ and ‘interdependence’ are fostered as the principles of international law espousing that ‘the fulfilment of one goal often depends or is interrelated, wholly or in part on other’ (Boas et al., 2016; Grant, 2007). The principles of ‘interdependence’ and ‘interrelatedness’ assumes that the implementation of one goal should not compromise the implementation of other goals, which mean each goal is indivisible (Boas et al., 2016).

‘Interrelatedness’ and ‘interdependence’ of the goals connect the institutions multifariously and improve the effectiveness of institutions by provisioning clarity in mandate and authority, as well as subsidiarity (Leonardi & Paraskevopoulos, 1996; Mathenjwa, 2018). As, UNESCO Report urges to adopt a collaborated approach to address the common problems and shall involve the diverse institutions (environmental, social and economic) (Bouckaert et al., 2018). EU Study approach is to create horizontal and vertical institutional collaboration and partnerships for SDG implementation developed upon integrated policies (Niestroy et al., 2019).

Integration of policies is the core of the SDGs due to their scope endeavouring to protect the diverse interests of everyone with the aim of ‘leaving no one behind.’ However, this integration is not simple; it is systematic, setting priorities in accordance with human needs (Kim, 2016). The ‘systemic integration’ in international law is practised in courts to interpret the two diverse international law instruments and to develop harmonisation (Le Blanc, 2015).

Meadowcroft et al (2005), Meuleman and Niestroy (2015), and Zeijl-Rozema et al (2008) prompt to take an integrated view of environmental, social and economic aspects to support policy ‘coherence’ and ‘cohesion.’ The EU Study following Biermann et al (2014) exhort to integrate the targets among the national and local mechanisms of

governments for effective implementation. The systemic integration forming ‘coherency’ and ‘cohesion’ is to link among concept and reality, and, science and risks, as practical aspects of policymaking (Collste et al., 2017; Le Blanc, 2015).

SDGs as systemic integration and interdependent arrangement of human needs puts forth to diminish discrimination (Salleh, 2016). Such global goals are implemented by streaming principles of ‘universality, inalienability and inclusiveness’ (Rudolf, 2020). ‘Universality,’ and ‘inalienability’ as principles of international law means that everyone is entitled to the goals in the form of adequate living, food, employment and good environment (Nanda, 2015). Further, ‘inclusiveness’ is to include everyone in the decision-making process as a matter of right and to ensure the protection of their interests (Parris & Kates, 2003; Piselli, 2019; Sands, 1995).

The EU Study and the UNESCO Report embed the principles of ‘universality, inclusiveness and inalienability’ to allow ‘public participation’ to ensure absoluteness and uncompromised position of each of the SDG (Bouckaert et al., 2018; Niestroy et al., 2019). Meuleman and Niestroy (2015) link the ‘participation’ with the goal of capacity building in order to strengthen the participation of the local governments. Zeijl-Rozema et al (2008) attributed ‘public participation’ a mechanism involving private groups and individuals influencing policy while securing their rights and leading towards consensus.

Public participation is an opportunity for accommodating the diverse interests of all the stakeholders to form consensual policies (Coenen, 2009). ‘Universality’ of SDGs by assimilating miscellaneous targets includes the public-at-large to ensure the ‘inalienable’ position of each goal through ‘consensual’ policymaking process (Lempert, 2017). Therefore, the elements of ‘consensus’ and ‘participation’ are intertwined with the principles of ‘universality, inclusiveness and inalienability’ in governance (Kuhn, 2020).

To ensure SDGs as human, social and environmental rights, and to guarantee ‘equitable’ and ‘proportional’ distribution of wealth and opportunity, and to maintain the equitability while exploiting natural resources calls for the impartial implementation of the law (Arajärvi, 2018). ‘Impartiality’ comes along with ‘equality’ and solicits to assure the implementation of rights to human ‘equally’ and ‘impartially’(Lwabukuna, 2016).

Biermann et al (2014) phase the principles of ‘impartiality and equality’ throughout the governance mechanisms beginning from the policymaking to effective implementation and equitable distribution of the outcomes. Zeijl-Rozema et al (2008) express ‘equality’ as equal footing providing societal preferences under the decisions if are in conjunction with the scientific evidence, connecting it with ‘coherence’ and ‘cohesion.’ However, the EU Study, UNESCO Report, and Meuleman and Niestroy (2015) stipulate that the impartial implementation heavily relies on an ‘open decision-making process’ to establish ‘institutional liability’ (Bouckaert et al., 2018; Niestroy et al., 2019).

The institutional integrity is maintained by impartial implementation of the law to secure the interests of each individual and heavily relies upon disclosure of information and independent oversight (Bowen et al., 2017). The mechanisms of open decision making and independent oversight are formulated utilising the principles of ‘openness’ and ‘liability’ (Alemanno, 2014). The principle of ‘openness’ is substantially operational to conduct transparent policymaking, and ‘liability’ is to develop self-accountability as well as independent review mechanisms (Bugaric, 2004; Curtin & Nollkaemper, 2005).

The principles of ‘openness and liability’ in international law reiterates the right to access the information and the makes institution answerable for consequences of their decisions (O’Connor & Azzarelli, 2011). The interplay among ‘openness and liability’ is due to

their functional attachment because institutions are held liable under the available information.

The EU Study and the UNESCO Report attaches the principle ‘openness’ with ‘liability,’ ‘impartiality’ and ‘equality’ in the direction to institute mechanisms for transparent government data, review of institutional decisions, and independent audits (Bouckaert et al., 2018; Niestroy et al., 2019). Meuleman and Niestroy (2015) ascertain the mechanisms of ‘openness’ and ‘liability’ to be strong enough in curbing corruption and promoting honesty conducive to protect the public interest. Therefore, the principles of ‘openness and liability’ are interlinked to shape the elements of ‘transparency’ and ‘accountability,’ generating a thriving effect in governance.

Given that, it is ascertained to resolve complexities, the principles of international law interfacing with the elements of governance focus on the implementation of the SDGs. These principles as extracted are ‘equity and proportionality,’ ‘precautionary measures and preventive action,’ ‘interrelatedness and interdependence,’ ‘systemic integration,’ ‘universality, inclusiveness, and inalienability,’ ‘impartiality and equality,’ and ‘openness and liability.’

These principles convey a possible path for successful reforms on institutional structures and functions as they focus on building the capacity of the institutions by symmetrising hierarchies through establishing the role of law delving targets. The epitome of 17 SDGs with the construal of 169 targets vibrantly restructures the preferences and forwards a principled approach, resolving further complexities (Hák et al., 2016). The target of one goal may prejudice the other, but if common principles are established the elements in governance are customised holistically (Maron et al., 2018). The targets of the SDGs

establish linkages of various goals with the principles of international law forwarding a way to determine the elements of implementation.

Therefore, to constitute a theoretical framework for the analysis of governance mechanism, the principles extracted are assessed with the targets of the SDGs for further clarification in terms of the usage. Building institutional orchestration and employing a practical shape to each of the principles, the examples from the literature are utilised with the citations of the relevant international law.¹² Yet, the principles are reorganised proficiently per their applicability by smearing a hierarchal method, starting from policymaking to effective implementation.¹³

4 The Role of International Law in Governance of SDGs

4.1 Universality, Inalienability and Inclusiveness

The principles of universality, inclusiveness and inalienability becoming significant in implementation of the SDGs are deep-rooted in the International Covenants on Civil and Political Rights, (1966) (ICCPR) and International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, (1966) (ICESCR). These covenants assert ‘equal and inalienable rights of all members of the human family as the foundation of freedom, justice and peace in the world by providing every individual the right and the opportunity to take part in the conduct of public affairs.’

¹² The International Law Treaties, Conventions and Declarations forwards diverse mechanisms envisioning the principles for Sustainable Development, See, (Lucas et al., 2014).

¹³ Normative hierarchy in international law is adopted to develop resilient administrative structures, such approach provides clarity in mandate of the institutions for effective implementation, See, (Shelton, 2006).

Based on the notion of the universality, inclusiveness and inalienability of human rights, ‘human development’ originating from the ICCPR and ICESCR is guaranteed under the United Nations Declaration on the Right to Development, (1987) (Development Declaration) encouraging participation of all segments. Development Declaration invites ‘to participate, contribute, and enjoy economic, social, cultural and political development, and it also implies the full realisation of the right of peoples to self-determination, which includes, the exercise of their inalienable right to full sovereignty over all their natural wealth and resources’ (Arts & Tamo, 2016).

The targets of SDG – 4 (Quality Education), SDG – 5 (Gender Equality), SDG – 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation), SDG – 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), induces participation of the youth, adults, women, local communities,(Bartram et al., 2018) and civil society respectively in securing their rights in each SDG (Bartram et al., 2018; Boeren, 2019; Pandey & Kumar, 2019; Parnell, 2016). The SDG – 16 (Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions) endorses participation of the public through representatives and promotes the involvement of the developing countries to secure SDGs (*Final List of Proposed Sustainable Development Goal Indicators*, 2016).

Hence, the principles of ‘universality, inalienability and inclusiveness’ are for the participation of each individual in governance to secure rights and protect their interests. Participation as a right evolving from the ICCPR and ICESCR is endorsed to secure environmental rights in a manner to commence adequate living standards (Steele, 2001). Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision-Making and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters, (1998) (Aarhus Convention) devises the public participation directly or through representatives in environmental law and policymaking.

(United Nations Conference Declaration on Environment and Development, (1992) that ‘environmental issues are best handled with the participation of all concerned citizens.’ Chapter 27, 28 and 29 of the Agenda 21 of the United Nations, Report of the World Summit on Sustainable Development, (2002) (UN Report) compels the governments to ensure participation of nongovernmental groups, local authorities, workers and trade-unions for decision-making.¹⁴ Similarly, the Johannesburg Declaration on Health and Sustainable Development, (2002) (Johannesburg Declaration) recognises that sustainable development requires broad-based participation in policy and decision making, and its implementation at regional, national and local levels.

The broad participation of the public and stakeholders is to originate consensus for a common agreement considering all the relevant issues (de Paula Contipelli, 2018). The best policies consider the diverse interests of everyone in the best interest of the whole community (Sperduti, 1976). Though the participation is mandatory, it is problematic, and a constrain in the decision-making process. However, consensus-building through participation is to ensure that the decision of any individual or group for their interests should not be able to force. Additionally, the decision-making process, while considering equitable and proportional outcomes, is supportive of removing analogous constraints (Phillips & Higgott, 1999).

SDGs are the outcome of consensus among global leadership, and it is seeking further consensus in policy development for implementation (Martin, 2015). The consensus forming SDGs is assisted by a continuous and long-term global negotiation through

¹⁴ Principle 27, and the Chapter 27 (Partnership with Non-Governmental Groups), 28 (Local Authorities) and 29 (Workers and Trade Unions) of the Agenda 21 of the (*United Nations, Report of the World Summit on Sustainable Development, 2002*) calls to engage the political, social and trade organisation in governance mechanisms, See, (Coenen, 2009, p. 21) p. 165-182.

sectoral, cross-sectoral, regional, national and local participation (*A Territorial Approach to the Sustainable Development Goals*, n.d.). As the Agenda 21 was approved by the consensus among the global leadership, and it promotes consensus among local populations by inviting the participation of youth and women. Chapter 28 of the Agenda 21 of the UN Report states that full participation (at various levels) shall be ensured to build consensus in implementation of sustainable development, and the Rio Declaration urges to adopt international consensus to handle the transboundary and global environmental problems.

The obligations under the ICCPR, ICESCR and Aarhus Convention in application of the principles of ‘universality, inclusiveness and inalienability’ with the endorsement of the Development, Rio and Johannesburg Declarations transform the element of ‘public participation’ in governance as horizontal and vertical participation of stakeholders, including, public, private, political and social groups (Fox, 1992). The participation as process formulates interactive activities among institutions, public, stakeholders and social interest groups leading towards consensual policies protecting the interests of everyone (Martens, 2020).

4.2 Systemic Integration

SDGs are systemically integrated, arising from the diverse instruments of the international law (Bruce & Stephenson, 2016; de Paula Contipelli, 2018). The principle of ‘systemic integration’ enshrined in the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties, (1969) is to resolve the conflicts among two diverse treaties while conducting interpretation. Systemic integration in global governance mode is referred to as a strategy that works with the goal-setting approach, and in treaty interpretation, provides and ensures harmonisation in the needs of the society and generations (Kim, 2016; Le Blanc,

2015). Integration of the diverse goals is to adopt coherence across the on-going policy development processes (McLachlan, 2005). More practical conduct of systemic integration is policy formation in conjunction with scientific information integrating the diverse policies to amplify harmonisation in institutions and law for implementation (Olawuyi, 2014). Integration of the economic, social and environmental policies as suggested by the global governance mechanisms puts forward the notion of amalgamation of the science, risk and knowledge (Christensen et al., 2011; *Integrating Environmental Risk Assessment*, 2015).

SDG – 1 and SDG – 2 (eradication of hunger and poverty) are derived from the ICESCR, (1966) and the WTO Agreement: Marrakesh Agreement Establishing the World Trade Organization, (1995). SDG – 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) and SDG – 13 (Climate Action) arises from the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, (1992), Kyoto Protocol , (1997), and Paris Agreement, (2016).

Targets of the SDGs are with similar suggestions to accommodate the diverse economic, social, environmental and scientific policies into a single framework. For example, SDG – 3 (Good Health and Well-Being) and SDG – 13 (Climate Action) valiantly demands the integration of health governance into national strategies and climate change measures into national policies, respectively (Cerf, 2019; Obergassel et al., 2017). SDG – 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth) and SDG – 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities) forwards a plan to integrate the trade assistance to developing countries, and to assimilate the resource efficiency, mitigation and adaptation in urban, semi-urban and rural areas respectively (Le Blanc, 2015; *Tracking Progress Towards Inclusive, Safe, Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Human Settlements*, 2018). SDG – 17 (Partnership for Goals) requires the systemic issues to be coordinated, and coherence to be established among the

institutions and policies (*Final List of Proposed Sustainable Development Goal Indicators*, 2016; De Wet & Vidmar, 2013).

This integration, in general, is observed in the Convention on Biological Diversity, (1992) (Biodiversity Convention), coercing to integrate as far as possible the conservation and sustainable use of the natural resources, into cross-sectoral policies. Chapter 8 of the Agenda 21 UN Report affirms the integration of social and environmental policies, and the Declaration of the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment, (1973) (Stockholm Declaration) urges to adopt approaches of development integrating the environmental protection.

International law is moving towards systemic integration of diverse instruments, as recently settled Paris Agreement to the UNFCCC is the integration of human rights into climate change (Brus, 2018). The Paris Agreement states, ‘to address climate change, should respect, promote and consider respective obligations on human rights.’ The interpretation of the international instruments suggests systemic integration to resolve conflicts between different interests (McLachlan, 2005). For example, Chapter 3 of Agenda 21 of the UN Report ‘suggests that factors creating policies for development, resource management, and poverty must be integrated’ (Palmans & Marysse, 2003; United Nations Conference on Environment and Development/Rio Declaration on Environment and Development, 1992). Chapter 10 of the Agenda 21 of the UN Report imposes an obligation to ensure that land and natural resources must integrate environmental, social and economic issues.

International law provides a way-forward to integrate the diverse interests of the society systemically. SDGs are to balance among the varying interests of different segments of the society and generations. SDGs demands an ecological threshold to protect the

environment and natural resources and affords equal importance to each concern (Hens & Nath, 2005). Although, the fragmentation of policies and institutions is an impediment, the systematisation of systemic integration is possibly a way-out (De Wet & Vidmar, 2013; Moreno-Lax, 2014). By taking systemic integration into account of governance integrates several precepts systematically, such as the science and information, risks and development, economy, environment and society (Roux & Desjardins, 2012). The outputs of shaping the elements of coherence and cohesion are to create co-policy instruments, accommodation of diverse and discursive policies or/and policy-coordination (Jansen, 2003).

4.3 Openness and Liability

Openness as a mechanism of ‘access to information’ is a notion of the ICCPR and attributed by the Special Rapporteur’s annual report that ‘access to information is obligation of the institutions’ (*Report of the Special Rapporteur, Promotion and Protection of the Right to Freedom of Opinion and Expression*, 1998).¹⁵ It means that the institutions are liable to issue information to the public for their access (Johnston, 2006). The principle of openness in international law is the backbone of decision-making and implementation processes protecting the right of access to specific information (Lebeck, 2006).

Access to the environmental information to the public is guaranteed under the Aarhus Convention. Similarly, the Stockholm and Rio Declarations urges to ensure access to the scientific and environmental information, as far as possible to each individual. More

¹⁵ The report of the Special Rapporteur directly oblige the States, however, for this research the institutions are referred generically and in theoretical reference, therefore the term ‘state’ is replaced with ‘institutions.’ See, (*Report of the Special Rapporteur, Promotion and Protection of the Right to Freedom of Opinion and Expression*, 1998)

specifically, Chapter 40 of Agenda 21 of the UN Report calls the institutions to ensure access to information of the environment and natural resources to the public.

On the other hand, liability in international law is to define the consequences attached to the violation of a primary obligation (Boyle, 1993). The core concern of liability is to establish mechanisms of responsibility and accountability to hold the institutions answerable. The Rio Declaration urges to legislate and establish mechanisms on liability for the victims of the environmental damage. The Johannesburg Declaration stated to have democratic and accountable institutions for sustainable development.

The mechanisms of holding institutions liable require additional review and evaluation systems. As stated in Chapter 27 of Agenda 21 of the UN Report to ‘create laws enabling nongovernmental groups a part of the review process and evaluation of the implementation and provide them opportunity to take legal action to protect the public interest.’ Such review and evaluation apparatuses are constructed by linking the mechanisms of transparency and accountability, as, the institutions are made liable through the available information.

SDG – 10 (Reduced Inequalities), SDG – 16 (Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions) and SDG – 13 (Climate Action) demands to form effective, credible, accountable, transparent and legitimate institutions to ensure a sustainable climate, society and economy by providing access to justice at all levels (*Final List of Proposed Sustainable Development Goal Indicators*, 2016). SDG – 17 (Partnerships for the Goals) declares that in order to create partnerships with the least developed countries, the preferential rules have to be transparent.

Due to private-public stakeholder integration in SDGs the principle of ‘liability’ is conceptualised to protect the whistle-blower and drives from preparing internal code of conduct mechanisms, not limited to the public authorities but extending to the private corporations (Buntaine, 2015). The Johannesburg Declaration broadens the application of the principle of ‘liability’ by insisting to enforce corporate accountability and transparency frameworks in order to hold private stakeholders liable. Hence, besides independent judicial and quasi-judicial bodies, the principle of ‘liability’ requires internal and public review mechanisms (Mahoney, 2008; Petersmann, 2008).

The obligations of the institutions under the ICCPR and Aarhus Convention with the application of the Stockholm, RIO and Johannesburg Declarations are to disclose the information of the activities or the interaction with the environment and natural resources and to establish mechanisms to hold institutions accountable. The elements of accountability and transparency are transformed as the mechanisms of open decision making, independent oversight, internal review and evaluation in governance (*Principles of Effective Governance for Sustainable Development*, n.d.).

4.4 Proportionality and Equity

The WTO Agreement clarifies that the trade and commerce through the expansion of production is with a pre-condition to raise living standards, ensuring full employment, and optimal use of the global resources with the aim of sustainable development. In furtherance, besides setting proportionality between trade and human development also sets out that exploitation of natural resources to be consistent with the environment, in order to maintain ecological balance.

The Development Declaration asserts that ‘necessary measures to be undertaken to ensure, equality of opportunity for all in their access to basic resources, education, health

services, food, housing, employment and the fair distribution of income.’ Correspondingly, the Stockholm and Rio Declarations impel that exploitation of resources is to be proportional with the environment and preservation of natural resources for future generations.

Proportionality prompts for equitable and optimum utilisation of natural resources as induced by the Biodiversity Convention, phasing out its objectives as ‘the conservation of biological diversity (emerges from) the sustainable use of its components and the fair and equitable sharing of the benefits arising out of the utilization of genetic resources.’ Moreover, the United Nations Convention on Law of the Sea, (1982) indicates ‘equitable and efficient utilisation of the resources,’ which means proportional exploitation of resources in order to protect the environment and interests of future generations.

The targets of SDGs – 1 (No Poverty) and SDG – 2 (Zero Hunger) are proportional to SDG – 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), demonstrating that economic development is for social resilience and to dispense the wealth and opportunity equitably (*Final List of Proposed Sustainable Development Goal Indicators*, 2016). SDG – 8 illustrates that sustainable economic growth is to guarantee employment and decent-working condition, which is a competent example of the operation of the proportionality principle. SDG – 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) and SDG – 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure) promotes sustainable and eco-friendly energy and infrastructure development for equitable exploitation of natural resources and the protection of the environment.

Therefore, the application of principles of proportionality and equity in governance with the element of equitability are for equitable and efficient utilisation of natural resources (Collins, 2007). Governing development with the principles of equity and proportionality

assures inter/intragenerational equity by synchronising environmental protection, equitable distribution of the outcomes, and preservation of the natural resources.

4.5 Precautionary Measures and Preventive Action

SDG – 13 states ‘take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts,’ as these impacts of climate change are due to ignoring precautionary measures and preventive action by the institutions (Ahmed et al., 2016). Adoption of these principles in governance is to provide long-term focus in policymaking to improve certainty and predictability. The certainty and predictability of institutions while functioning improves their capacity, efficiency and responsiveness (Stirling, 2006).

Biodiversity Convention enshrines the principles of precautionary measures and preventive action in the form of ‘impact assessment’ prior to the conduct of any project having likely adverse effects on the environment. The Johannesburg Declaration recognises that ‘impact assessment’ is to take long-term perspectives in governance to achieve sustainable development. Chapter 15 of Agenda 21 of the UN Report urges to conduct long-term research for the protection and conservation of the biodiversity and ecosystems for environmental benefits.

Both the principles of precautionary measures and prevention action are enshrined in the Chapter 38 of the Agenda 21 of the UN Report and the Stockholm Declaration, urging the adoption and promotion of the policies to protect and improve the environment by undertaking careful planning and managing the natural resources. Policymaking and implementation in accordance with these measures is to be rational, sound, consistent and

long-term, determining the scientific-information, and concept and reality.¹⁶ Therefore, these measures improve the quality of prediction and certainty of the institutions and promotes optimum utilisation of natural resources and minimum harm to the environment.

4.6 Interrelatedness and Interdependence

SDGs, systemically integrated and proportional to each other are interrelated and interdependent. This interconnected nature of the SDGs seeks collective institutional efficiency for implementation in governance. ICESCR urges to cooperate in order to ensure ‘adequate food, clothing and housing, and to the continuous improvement of living conditions.’ Similarly, the Biodiversity Convention prompts to cooperate as far as possible for the conservation of the ecosystems.

Therefore, SDG – 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities) calls to strengthen the interconnections among the urban governance, municipalities and local systems (Dick, 2016). The SDG – 17 (Partnerships for Goals) strategises to strengthen the implementation of SDGs via global partnerships, domestic resource mobilisation, international support, technology sharing, and capacity-building (*Final List of Proposed Sustainable Development Goal Indicators*, 2016). Specifically focusing the developing countries, it demands to enhance the policy cohesion and coordination, create multi-stakeholder partnerships and to resource strategies for efficient outcomes (Adams & Judd, 2016).

¹⁶ Policymaking shall be with a rational, sound, consistent and long-term, approach, taking the scientific-information, and concept and reality into account for implementation of the sustainable development. See, (*Case Concerning the Gabčíkovo-Nagymaros Dam (Hungary v Slovakia)*, 1997)

The Rio Declaration is with the goal of establishing a new and equitable global partnership through new levels of cooperation among States, key sectors and societies and people. In addition, the Johannesburg Declaration taking the interconnected policies of SDGs compels to enroot ‘a collective responsibility to advance and strengthen the interdependent and mutually reinforcing pillars of economic development, social development and environmental protection at the local, national, regional and global levels.’ Formulating SDGs implementation as a collective responsibility of the institutions improve adaptive capacity, competence and collaboration (Meuleman, 2012).

As professed in the Johannesburg Declaration that ‘the establishment of stable partnerships with all major groups and respecting the independent and important role of them is the future.’ The purpose of creating such partnerships is to banish underdevelopment forever, and rapid increase in access to basic requirements. Therefore, the principles of interrelatedness and interdependence facilitate institutional networks, not only for the effective implementation but also to respond efficiently to the matters raised (Feiock, 2009; Secco et al., 2017). Further, the collaboration and cooperation among institutions improve the hierarchal lines of command resolving complexities and formulating partnerships (Monkelbaan, 2019). These partnerships by integrating institutions vertically and horizontally in accordance with their targets foster adaptation, and capacity building (Pinto, 2004).

4.7 Impartiality and Equality

SDG – 16 (Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions) distinguish the principle of ‘impartial implementation of law’ to ensure ‘equal access to justice.’ Equality before the law and its impartial implementation is the notion of the ‘rule of law’ interpreted by various organisations under the auspices of United Nations, including, International Court of

Justice, United Nations Environmental Programme, and United Nations Development Programme (Hopkins, 1991).

Impartial implementation of international law in sustainable development serves as a yardstick to measure the institutional acts while protecting the rights of the generations (Fontanelli et al., 2009). It requires that the institutions shall enact the policies as devised by international law, as the Rio Declaration asserts that States shall enact effective environmental legislation, standards, management objectives and priorities reflecting the environment and development.

Biodiversity Convention backing the notion of 'equality' nurtures fair and just implementation of the law to share the benefits arising from the natural resources by establishing mechanisms within a democratic and transparent system of governance. Thus, impartial implementation of the law is assisted with the mechanisms of transparency and participation.

Moreover, impartial implementation of law substantiates the role of the public concerning environmental protection as their responsibility (Magraw, 2014). This responsibility includes identifying threats, catalysing political action, playing an active role to shape laws, and monitoring the effective implementation of laws. The impartiality serves to ensure equality among the humans by advocating the universality and inclusiveness between the generations.

Therefore, impartial implementation of the law for equality devises the duties and responsibilities of the institutions to guarantee inter/intragenerational justice (Maggio, 1996). At the same time, effective implementation of law depends on appropriate promulgation of the law, which also promotes the stability of the institutions (Nwabuzor,

2005). Correspondingly, the impartial implementation of the law for equal treatment tend to be mutually reinforcing with all other principles (Rigobon & Rodrik, 2005).

<i>Integrating Multilevel Governance</i>	<i>Elements of Governance</i>	<i>Principles of International Law</i>	<i>Shape of Governance</i>	<i>Results of Governance</i>
<i>Good Governance</i>	Consensus and Participation	Universality, Inalienability and Inclusiveness	Horizontal and Vertical Participation of Stakeholders and Public	Common Agreement, Sound-Policy Making.
	Coherence and Cohesion	Systemic Integration	Integration of Economic-Social-Environmental Instruments.	Co-policy Instruments, Integrating Science-Risk-Information-Knowledge
	Transparency	Openness	Monitoring and Reporting Open Decision Making	Public Access to Information
	Accountability	Liability	Review and Evaluation Independent Oversight	Decision-Makers Responsible to Citizens Eradication of Corruption
<i>Effective Governance</i>	Certainty and Predictability	Precaution and Preventive-Action	Long- and Short-Term Perspectives Foresightedness	Appropriate Political/Administrative Frameworks, Policy Continuity
	Efficiency and Responsiveness	Interrelatedness Interdependence	Institutional Networks and Management, Decentralisation and Discretion in Implementation, Authority and Subsidiarity.	Share of Responsibilities Adaptive Capacity Competence, Collaboration And Synergies
<i>Equitable Governance</i>	Equitability	Proportionality and Equity	Equitable and Efficient Utilisation of Natural Resources Proportionality among Environment-Development-Preservation of Natural Resources	Equitable Distribution of Wealth and Opportunity Protection of Environment Preservation of Natural Resources Intergeneration Equity
	Rule of Law	Impartiality and Equality	Duties and Responsibilities	Equal and Equitable Implementation of Law, Intergenerational Justice

5 Conclusion

In existing scenario of institutional conflicts, the existing approaches of governance are impractical in implementation of global goals at regional, national and local levels. The literature integrating governance into SDGs as its integral part offers a way-forward. Nevertheless, the mechanism to achieve SDGs lacks seriousness because current approaches lacks principled application of international law. Therefore, this research extracted and adopted the principles of international law in a binding manner, inducing an interplay among the elements of the governance leading to SDGs. This research suggests that the implementation of SDGs is back and forth with global perspectives

involving institutions up-to local levels. The necessity is to create harmonisation among the institutions are every level. This may be achieved by the principles provided through this research because they are with the ability to thrive in accordance with the targets of the SDGs. These principles under international law instruments are shaping the elements of governance in a manner that institutional coordination with subjugated perspectives is formed. Moreover, these principles are developing the international law with governance mechanisms for implementation of SDGs.

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